

Studies on Bis-N-phenylhydroxamic acids as Metal-complexing ligands : Part IV-Dissociation constants of the ligands and the starting dicarboxylic acids

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In previous communications¹ the syntheses of R_sH_2 , R_rH_2 , R_aH_2 and R_pH_2 and of some of their metal complexes have been reported. The coordinating abilities of these ligands are being studied by determining the formation constants of the metal complexes. Since the evaluation of the formation constants required the knowledge of the acid dissociation constants (K_2^* and K_1^*) of the ligands, they have been determined in (1 : 2) aqueous-ethanol as most of the ligands and complexes are only slightly soluble in (1 : 1) aqueous-ethanol. In order to find out any relation between the dissociation constants of the ligands and those of the corresponding dicarboxylic acids, the present work also includes the determination of acid dissociation constants (K'_2 and K'_1) of the corresponding dicarboxylic acids under identical conditions.

EXPERIMENTAL

All the chemicals used were either A.R. quality or properly purified.

NaOH solution was standardised with hydrazine sulphate and the strength was further verified with potassium bi-iodate.

pH measurements were made with a Cambridge (portable type) pH-meter. Electrode system consisted of a glass electrode and a saturated calomel electrode (as reference electrode) with a 2M-sodium nitrate solution bridge. The pH-meter was calibrated with aqueous buffers.

Measurements were performed in (1 : 2) aqueous ethanol by titrating potentiometrically a 100 ml solution containing known amount of ligand (in the order of 0.003–0.005M) and perchloric acid with a standard 0.3230M NaOH solution at a temperature $33 \pm 1^\circ$. Ionic strength of the medium ($\mu = 0.25$) was maintained constant by adding requisite amount of $NaClO_4$. The results reported here are based on duplicate titrations made under identical conditions.

In order to determine the final acid concentration, a graphical method was employed. For this purpose pH values of a number of $HClO_4$ solutions of known strength in (1 : 2) aqueous ethanol and having the same ionic strength ($\mu = 0.25$) were plotted against negative logarithm of acid concentration. The final acid concentrations were extrapolated from the

1. N. N. Ghosh and D. K. Sarkar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1968, **45**, 550; 1969, **46**, 528; 1970, **47**, 562.

corresponding pH assuming that the behaviour of strong acids is the same in aqueous and mixed solvents².

The values of \bar{n}_H were then calculated and plotted against corresponding pH values. K_2^* , K_1^* as well as K'_2 , K'_1 were evaluated from linear plots³ of

$$\frac{[H^+](1-\bar{n}_H)}{\bar{n}_H} \quad \text{against} \quad \frac{[H^+]^2(2-\bar{n}_H)}{\bar{n}_H}$$

using only these \bar{n}_H values that were between 0.5 and 1.5, as shown in Fig. 1 and Fig. 2 and results are stated in Table I.

TABLE I

Dicarboxylic acids	pK'_2	pK'_1	$\frac{1}{2}(pK'_2+pK'_1)$	Ligands	pK_2^*	pK_1^*	$\frac{1}{2}(pK_2^*+pK_1^*)$
Succinic acid	5.36	6.58	5.97	$R_S H_2$	9.37	10.37	9.87
Glutaric acid	5.64	6.65	6.05	$R_G H_2$	9.36	10.46	9.91
Adipic acid	5.77	6.49	6.13	$R_A H_2$	9.91	10.01	9.96
Pimelic acid	5.95	6.65	6.30	$R_P H_2$	9.87	10.22	10.05

Fig. 1.

Fig. 2.

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DISCUSSION

The order of variation of average pK values of *bis-N-phenylhydroxamic acids* parallels that of the corresponding dicarboxylic acids when they were measured under identical conditions. On plotting, the average pK^* values of ligands i.e., $\frac{1}{2}(pK_2^* + pK_1^*)$ against the average pK' values of dicarboxylic acids i.e., $\frac{1}{2}(pK'_2 + pK'_1)$ a straight line would be obtained. Similar relation has also been observed in the cases of some *N-acyl N-phenylhydroxyl-amines*⁴.

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